

LABORATORY PROGNOSTIC MARKERS OF ANEMIA IN PATIENTS WITH JUVENILE RHEUMATOID ARTHRITIS

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Abstract. Anemia initiated by juvenile rheumatoid arthritis (JRA) has its own specific pathogenesis, which was revealed in detail in the present study. There is an inverse relationship between the activity of the process of juvenile rheumatoid arthritis, caused by activation of the cytokine system, in particular interleukin 6 and erythropoietin stimulating factor of blood serum ($p < 0.001$). Ferritin as an acute phase indicator increased in patients in groups 1 and 2 to 104.6 ± 39.4 and 212.7 ± 14.8 ng/ml, however, it did not in any way reflect the state of iron depot in the body $p < 0.001$ in all comparison groups and between themselves. Ferroportin in patients with mild anemia was 0.21 ± 0.04 ng/ml, which indicates its decrease. Based on this, we can conclude that the more ferritin increases, ferroportin decreases in direct proportion to it.

Keywords: JRA, anemia, ferritin, erythropoietin, ferroportin.

Relevance of the problem. Anemia is one of the most common extra-articular manifestations in patients suffering from rheumatoid arthritis (RA), with a reported prevalence ranging from 15 to 60%. It is well known that anemia in JRA is associated with higher disease activity, worse outcome parameters, and increased mortality. The opinion of most researchers agrees that anemia of chronic disease (ACD) most often prevails in patients with RA, with the combination of ACD and IDA in second place, with the overall prevalence of anemia ranging from 30 to 70% [7]. Others have suggested that in groups of patients with well-controlled disease, IDA may be more common. In studies conducted in the UK in 2011, more IDA was detected in patients with RA than ACD [4]. Regardless of the type of anemia, according to the unanimous opinion of researchers, treatment of anemia should begin with treatment of the underlying disease [6,7,10]. Systemic-onset juvenile chronic arthritis (JCA) is associated with high circulating levels of interleukin-6 (IL-6) and is often complicated by severe microcytic anemia, the pathogenesis of which is unclear [2].

In addition, shortened erythrocyte half-life, suppressed erythropoietin response to anemia, and inhibition of erythroid cell differentiation by inflammatory mediators further contribute to disease-specific IS [11]. Studies have confirmed that patients with active JRA often have low hemoglobin (Hgb) levels due to inflammation and/or iron deficiency [1]. In the absence of inflammation, serum ferritin, as an indicator of total body iron stores, is the most useful parameter for differentiating ACD from IDA [5]. However, in acute and chronic inflammatory diseases, high serum concentrations ferritin are the result of increased secretion by iron-containing macrophages. In addition, serum ferritin is an acute phase protein that is induced by inflammatory mediators [8]. Thus, in inflammatory conditions, ferritin loses its diagnostic value as an indicator of total iron stores in the body.

Several biomarkers have been studied for their ability to detect iron deficiency in the presence of inflammation. Among them, soluble transferrin receptor (sTfR) is the biomarker that is most commonly used in clinical practice. [9]. Among several markers studied for their ability to detect true iron deficiency in inflammatory conditions, sTfR is the most commonly used biomarker

in clinical practice and is thought to be independent of inflammation [9]. Despite the huge amount of research in this direction, today the question of the pathogenesis and course of anemia in patients with juvenile rheumatoid arthritis remains open.

Purpose of the study. To study laboratory prognostic markers of anemia in patients with juvenile rheumatoid arthritis.

Material and methods. 129 patients with JRA aged 3 to 18 years were examined, of which 119 (92.2%) had the articular form and 10 (7.8%) had the articular-visceral form of the disease. The duration of the disease ranged from 3 months to 8 years. The duration of the disease ranged from 3 months to 8 years. All patients were divided into two groups: a main group of 99 children diagnosed with JRA and with anemic syndrome and a comparison group of 30 children diagnosed with JRA without signs of anemia. In addition to traditional clinical and laboratory studies, a blood test was performed for rheumatoid factor, C - reactive protein, erythropoietin, ferroportin, ferritin, serum iron, hemoglobin equivalent in reticulocytes RET- He, IL 6, radiography of joints. The activity of the JRA was assessed based on a clinical examination, the nature of the articular syndrome and the JADAS 10 index. The functional activity of patients was assessed according to the Steinbrocker criteria.

Results and discussion. Of the 129 JRA patients examined, 99 (76.7%) were diagnosed with anemia. According to the criteria for diagnosing anemia and its severity, based on the hemoglobin concentration, all patients were divided into groups with mild - 63.6% and moderate - 36.4% severity. There were no patients with severe profound anemia with hemoglobin less than 60 g/l. Among the examined patients, 36 were diagnosed with a moderate degree of anemia and 63 with a mild degree of the disease. 47 boys and 52 girls (Figure 1).

Figure 1. Distribution of JRA patients with anemia by severity

As can be seen from Table 2, in patients with JRA there is a tendency to decrease the content of red blood cells, which also corresponds to the directly proportional severity of the level of hemoglobin in the blood, thus it can be argued that there is a direct correlation between these parameters. A strong positive correlation was revealed between the hemoglobin concentration and the number of red blood cells ($r = 0.66$), and the color index ($r = 0.69$).

The number of leukocytes, as a distinctive sign of an active inflammatory process, in sick children was slightly higher than that of the comparison group, in children with mild anemia it was higher - $11.42 \times 10^9/l$ (with a range of M 14.5 - m 9.9), and in the group with a moderate degree of anemia - $14.01 \times 10^9/l$ (with a range of M 17.3 - m 11.2) ($P \leq 0.05$), with the age norm - from 4 to

9 * 10⁹/l, with a shift The leukoformula in sick children is observed more to the left, as evidenced by the greater detection of band neutrophils relative to the comparison group.

Table 2.

Peripheral blood parameters of patients with JRA

Indicators	Comparison group n =30	Mild anemia n= 63	Moderate degree of anemia n= 36
Hemoglobin, g /l	120,7±3,6	100,33±10,6 ¹	88,64±8,5 ^{1,2}
Red blood cells, x10 ¹² /l	4,45±1,25	3,12±0,75 ¹	3,02±0,15 ¹
Color index	0,85±0,01	0,7±0,02	0,7±0,01
Reticulocytes	5:1000	4:1000	2:1000
Platelets, x10 ⁹ /l	233,5±30,3	245,3±35,8	215,4±13,6
Leukocytes, x10 ⁹ /l	10,7±1,5	11,42±3,3	14,01±2,9 ²
Band neutrophils, %	1,1±0,7	3,08±0,15 ¹	3,64±0,88 ¹
Segmented neutrophils, %	65,3±3,2	75,71±4,29 ¹	70,1±1,88 ¹
Eosinophils, %	2,1±0,2	5,06±0,06 ¹	5,04±0,04 ¹
Lymphocytes, %	26,4±1,1	20,8±2,6 ¹	29,1±1,5 ^{1,2}
Monocytes, %	5,06±0,3	3,8±0,2	3,81±0,5
ESR, mm/hour	14,28±0,6	28,6±1,1	35,2±3,3 ²

Note: significant difference (P <0.05) compared; 1 – with control values, 2 – with values of the mild anemia group.

Among immature granulocytes, there were such young forms as metamyelocytes and myelocytes. In children with JRA, the number of lymphocytes did not differ significantly from the group of children without anemic syndrome, however, an increase in this indicator took place, but it was not possible to isolate their increase relative to the comparison group, since due to the peculiarities of age norms 24 - 60x10⁹/l, the indicators are within the normal range.

Analysis of EPO values in the peripheral blood of patients with JRA showed that, with fluctuations from 12.0 to 25.8 mIU /ml, in none of the patients, both with anemia and without existing signs of anemia, the content of the factor was not lower than normal values. This can be explained by the normal functioning of the kidneys, which are not affected by ongoing inflammatory processes in the body of a child with JRA.

Consequently, patients with JRA generally have a normal level of EPO as their distinguishing feature, which in turn indicates erythropoietin independence of the development of anemia in JRA.

However, when studying EPO in relation to the degree of anemia, a decrease in EPO content in the group of patients with moderate anemia can be observed (Table 4) . Upon detailed study, it becomes clear that EPO decreases due to the activation of IL6, an inflammatory cytokine that blocks EPO. Thus, it can be argued that there is a cytokine-mediated decrease in the

concentration of EPO in the blood serum. And the development of anemia is accompanied by its own etiopathogenesis, which is not typical for known anemias.

Next, we studied transport proteins depending on the degree of anemia (Table 3.)

Table 3.

The content of erythropoietin (mIU /ml) and transport proteins in the blood serum of patients with JRA, depending on the degree of anemia

Index	Comparison group n =30	Mild anemia n= 63	Moderate degree of anemia n=36	Confidence factor (p)
EPO mIU /ml↓	38,8±2,2	20,3±3,1	12,1±1,3	<0,001 ^{1,2}
IL 6 mIU /ml	5,8±0,02	12,5±0,97	16,4±2,1	<0,001 ^{1,2}
Ferritin ng /ml↑	35,3±12,1	104,6±39,4	212,7±14,8	<0,001 ^{1,2}
Ferroportin ng/ml ↓	0,25±0,02	0,21±0,04	0,16±0,01	<0,001 ^{1,2}
Transferrin, mg/ dl ↑	230,6±15,7	290,3±21,1	315,7±10,4	<0,001 ^{1,2}

Notes: Ferritin reference values for children, according to the reagent instructions, they range from 5 to 100 ng / m l, transferrin 200-300 mg / dl, ferroportin 0.2-0.3 ng / ml.

¹ - group of patients with mild anemia compared to the control group, ² - group of patients with moderate anemia compared to the control group.

By studying the indicator of transport protein function, we discovered patterns that helped reveal the pathogenesis of the development of anemia in children with JRA, as well as what happens to the proteins responsible for the transfer of iron molecules immediately after absorption. Ferritin as an acute-phase indicator increased in patients in groups 1 and 2 to 104.6 ± 39.4 and 212.7 ± 14.8 ng / m l, however, it did not in any way reflect the state of iron depot in the body $p < 0.001$ in all comparison groups and among themselves, i.e. The greater the clinical manifestations of juvenile rheumatoid arthritis, the higher ferritin became. Ferroportin in patients with mild anemia was 0.21 ± 0.04 ng / ml, which indicates its decrease, but with an increase in the degree of anemia, it began to decrease significantly $p < 0.001$ and in the group with moderate anemia it was 0.16 ± 0.01 ng / ml. Based on this, we can conclude that the more ferritin increases, ferroportin decreases in direct proportion to it.

Another transport protein, transferrin, had a high degree of confidence in its increase in the blood, which means the body's compensatory work to increase the uptake of iron molecules, so in patients with mild anemia it was 290.3 ± 21.1 mg/dl, while in in the comparison group it was 230.6 ± 15.7 mg/ dl ($p < 0.001$). In patients who developed moderate anemia, transferrin was 315.7 ± 10.4 mg/ dl, a high level of significance ($p < 0.001$) between both study groups.

Conclusions. Thus, laboratory prognostic markers of anemia in patients with juvenile rheumatoid arthritis is the determination of erythropoietin, a soluble transferrin receptor ferritin, transferrin and IL 6. Based on the results of our studies, we can come to the conclusion that The development of anemia in children with JRA is characterized by both qualitative and quantitative

changes in red blood cells and gross disturbances of the protein transport function for the absorption of iron in the child's body.

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